

Study of Dissimilar Welding Microstructure of Duplex Stainless Steel SFA 2205 with High Strength Low Alloy Steel A387-GR.11 Welded by TIG Process

Seyyed Moslem Mousavi Khademi¹, Ali Shafiee², Abbas Najafizadeh³
School of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, Foulad institute of technology, Esfahan, Iran¹
Supervisor: Foulad university of technology²
Advisor: Foulad university of technology³

Abstract- In this paper, the dissimilar welding microstructure of the duplex stainless steel SFA 2205 with the high strength low alloy A378 Gr.11 was studied. The microstructure investigations indicated that the weld obtained has a two-phase structure, including dendritic and interdendritic areas. A high hardness transition area was detected in the interface of the A378 low alloy steel and ER 309L metal filler. An unmixed area was observable at the melting boundary of SFA2205 duplex steel and both austenitic and duplex filler metals. The results showed that for joining the two-phase stainless steel SFA2205 with the high strength low alloy A378 Gr.11, using the metal filler ER2209 is more appropriate as a result of forming a more suitable properties microstructure.

Index Terms- Duplex stainless steel, Dissimilar welding, Chromium-Molybdenum steel, high strength low alloy steel, Microstructure, Transition area.

I. INTRODUCTION

Dissimilar weldments have been widely used in the oil and gas industry because of economic benefits as well as the full advantage of outstanding performance of two different metals, such as strength and corrosion resistance. With the development of oil and gas exploitation in deep water, more and more duplex stainless steels (DSS) have been used in the flowline; however, low alloy steels are used in the cool end flowline section for economic consideration. Therefore, dissimilar weld joints are unavoidable. The properties of dissimilar welding joints and even the feasibility of welding processes are influenced by many factors, for example, carbon migration from the low alloy side, microstructure gradient, and different residual stress situations across different regions of weld metal [1].

Due to its excellent toughness, weldability, resistance to stress corrosion cracking and higher strength, Duplex Stainless Steel (DSS) is widely used in many fields such as petroleum, chemical industry, and architecture and pharmaceuticals industry. With the development of DSS, deeply research have been made on its microstructure, mechanical properties, corrosion resistance and weldability. There are many issues associated with the joining of dissimilar materials, depending on the materials being joined and process employed. Many general problems are encountered during welding and in the resultant weldments such as carbon migration, the differences

in thermal expansion coefficients and electrochemical property variations in the weldment. Dissimilar metal joints between low alloy chromium molybdenum ferritic steels and austenitic stainless steels are widely used in industries like power generation and petrochemical plants [2].

The most important phenomenon in this type of joints is carbon migration from ferritic steel into weld metal, creating a carbon depleted zone. This zone in the HAZ of low alloy steel is susceptible to creep failure. There also exists a transition zone or so called partially mixed zone in the weldment of these joints, where mixing between the base metal and the filler metal is incomplete. The other microstructural feature seen in the weldment, is the appearance of type II boundary, found parallel to the fusion line. These microstructural features frequently appear in the dissimilar joint of Duplex stainless steel and low alloy ferritic steel.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this paper, 2205 two-phase stainless steel and A378 GR.11 high strength low alloy steel (Chromium-Molybdenum) sheets were used as the base metals. Two filler metals of ER309L and ER2209 were utilized at constant input heat and current to join the aforementioned steels.

2.4 mm diameter wires were employed for root pass and next passes. Table 1 presents the chemical composition of the base

and filler metals. The leg of weld root and root distance were considered 1.5 mm and 2 mm, respectively. A schematic of joint design conducted based on AWS D1.1 standard is shown in Fig. 1. The tungsten arc welding method under the influence of shielding gas with a constant current type and a negative electrode (GTAW-DCEN) was employed in position 1G and four passes. In order to protect the welding pool, argon gas with a purity of 99.9% and a flow rate of 12 l/min was used. The welding process was conducted manually and by an experienced and capable welder. And a preheating temperature of 150°C was considered for A378 steel, which was controlled with the help of thermal gypsum during the process [1, 2]. After that, the samples were prepared for metallography and their surface was sanded and polished by SiC sandpapers No. 80 to 200. The samples were then etched by a solution of nital and marble. To more precisely study the microstructure of different areas of the welding samples and type of fracture, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) model TESCAN-VEGA3 made in the Czech Republic was utilized. Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) was used to investigate the elements available in different parts of joints created in the samples.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows the microstructure of SAF 2205 two-phase stainless steel, which is taken by optical and scanning electron microscopy. As can be seen, the microstructure only consists of two phases of layered ferrite (base phase) and austenite (prominent phase). Figure 3(a) illustrates an optical picture of the microstructure of A387 low alloy steel. The microstructure of this steel includes fine perlite and ferrite; the perlite structure is not clearly detectable in low magnification optical microscopy (OM) pictures but the layered structure is more clear with high magnification, as shown in Fig. 3(b). The microstructure of ER309L weld metal is presented by OM and SEM. The weld metal structure related to ER309L has an austenitic matrix with skeletal ferrite dendrites whose appearance is an indication of solidification occurrence in the manner of FA, i.e., the solidification starts in the form of initial ferrite and the austenite phase is then formed through a peritectic-eutectic reaction [2]. Depending on the type of solidification, ferrite can be in the form of skeletal (vermicular), reticular, or needle in the welding structure; when the cooling rate of the welding is mediocre or the ratio of C_{req}/N_{req} is low, a skeletal ferrite is created [3].

Figure 5 indicates the elemental analysis of ER 309L weld metal. As can be seen, the maximum amount of elements available in the weld metal is related to iron, chromium, and nickel. As shown in Fig. 6, dendritic microstructure ferrite and austenite phases are created by high cooling rates. Austenite and ferrite uniformly distribute in the weld metal and there are no harmful intermetallic and secondary phases in the weld metal. The solid-state transformation of ferrite to austenite

starts with lowering the temperature. Austenite nucleates from ferrite in the weld metal of two-phase steels in three ways, including in the form of grain boundary at the grain boundaries of ferrite (GBA), in the form of widmanstätten layers (WA) that start from grain boundaries and grow inside the grains, and in the form of intergranular sediments (IGA). The probability of austenite nucleation in the form of widmanstätten and intergranular flakes increases by increasing the input heat (the reduction of the cooling rate) because reheating of the welded segment causes more diffusion, leading to further growth of available austenite and/or nucleation of new austenite [4]. Figure 7 shows the elemental analysis of the weld metal ER2209. At the interface of the base metal, i.e., A387 steel, there is a fine transition zone at the melting boundary between both weld metals and A387 steel. The transition zone can be initiated from the difference in the crystal structure of the weld and base metals, concentration gradient at the melting boundary, and growth kinetic in the welding. The second type of boundary (initiated from dissimilar metals joint) is formed at the interface between the base metal A387 and the weld metal in using both filler metals of ER309 and ER2209. This boundary is formed at the freezing rate for the duration of cooling of the weld where the epitaxial growth is stopped and allowed that the austenite grains grow along the melting boundary [3, 5]. The nature of this boundary is martensite and/or rod carbides formed of Fe_3C , which results in increasing hardness in this boundary [6]. Figure 8 indicates a microscopic picture of the interface of the base metal 2205 and both consuming weld metals of ER309 and ER2209. A complete uniform interface all over the weld boundary is observable. The heat-affected zone in steel 2205 has a lower area compared to steel A387; this is attributable to the metallurgical properties of stainless steel and the very high thermal conductivity of these steels. The exact determination of phase equilibrium metallography in the HAZ of the two-phase stainless steel is almost impossible [7].

As can be seen in Fig. 8, the heat-affected zone has a lower amount of austenite compared to the base and weld metals, and the ferrite structure forms most of its composition. The microstructure of the heat-affected zone in the weldings of two-phase stainless steel has a nonequilibrium ratio of ferrite and austenite due to higher cooling rates initiated from welding [3].

There is an unmixed zone between the base and weld metals because a part of the base metal (steel 2205), which is present in the vicinity of the pool, is melted and is solidified again without mixing with the weld metal; therefore, this zone has a chemical composition close to the base metal [8, 9]. It is generally expressed that three tandem phenomena, including dissolution of austenite during heating, growth of ferrite grains, and transformation of delta ferrite to austenite during cooling, in the heat-affected zone of the two-phase stainless

steel occur during welding and under the influence of thermal cycles initiated from welding [10].

IV. CONCLUSION

- The filler metal ER2209 caused the reduction of sediment of the brittle nitride phase and the filler metal ER309L was resistant against solidification crack.
- There were a transition area and a partial mixture for the filler metals of ER309L and ER2209 at the interface of A387 steel, respectively; also, there was a complete continuous structure in addition to some unmixed areas and a ferrite structure at the heat-affected zone in addition to an unmixed area having more width for the filler metals of ER309L and ER2209 at the interface of SFA2205, respectively.
- the filler metal ER2209 is more suitable for joining two-phase stainless steel 2205 and high strength low alloy steel A387GR.11 because of creating a joint with a more continuous and predominant microstructure.

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